

Playing the Design: Creating Soundscapes through Playful Interaction

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ABSTRACT

This study takes inspiration from provocative design methods to gain knowledge on sound preferences regarding future vehicles' designed sounds. A particular population subset was a triggering component of this study: people with hearing impairments. To that aim, we have developed a public installation in which to test a hypothetical futuristic city square. It includes three electrical vehicles whose sound can be designed by the visitor. The interface allows the user to interact and play with a number of provided sonic textures within a real-time web application, thus "playing" the design. This opens a design space of three distinct sounds that are mixed into an overall soundscape presented in a multichannel immersive environment. The paper describes the design processes involved.

1. INTRODUCTION

This project intended to develop and test an exploratory interface able to support the sound design of hypothetical vehicles in a near-future soundscape. The results have been shared publicly in collaboration with *Tekniska* (the National Museum of Science and Technology) in Stockholm under the format of a physical, audio-visual, interactive installation in which the visitors could manipulate an audio synthesis environment in real-time. In this paper, the interface and the underlying design process are explained, as well as the resulting installation where users can interact with, we argue, thought-provoking sound designs. One aim is to make participation accessible to everyone in both composing the soundscapes and in providing data from their interactions.¹

This study is part of a larger project *Fictitious Soundscapes* in which we would like to address, in particular, people with hearing impairments and their sonic preferences. This heterogeneous group is at risk of not being included in sound design processes, but rather being passively accounted for in terms of adherence to formal regulations and guidelines such as the speech intelligibility index and noise exposure levels.

¹ Tekniska has an outspoken Design-for-All policy and our installation was planned in collaboration with their accessibility manager; see also <https://www.tekniskamuseet.se/en/visit/prepare-for-your-visit/>.

In order to address the challenge outlined above, the study has a twofold approach to design: First, the development and implementation of an interface for user testing, including the sound synthesis engines and a museum installation, and second, the museum visitors' sound designing process which includes how the sonic components that compromise the resulting soundscape are realized and how they actually sound. With these two understandings of "design", the museum visitors will thus playfully manipulate and change the components of the soundscape but within a delimited design space. As such, the end result is a soundscape design that is not intended to anticipate or advise a future reality but to provide insight into a particular subset of the complex issue of sound perception and appreciation. As introduced previously, a central aspect studied in this project is how to design a user-friendly interactive environment through which visitors can provide feedback on a number of design materials and variations by manipulating and refining them, ultimately co-designing the soundscape. Again, the focus here is not specifically placed on the evaluation of the sonic materials employed and resulting sonic textures by visitors, but on the interactive environment allowing such co-design processes.

In our project *Fictitious Soundscapes* we, therefore, investigate a specific method intended to provide feedback on sonic preferences for potential future city soundscapes with particular attention on "designed" sounds, i.e. specifically conceived and added as an overlay responding to different functional (e.g. safety) and potentially aesthetic reasons. Safety and aesthetics are today debated concerns when dealing with the presence of relatively silent electric vehicles in urban public environments and these have been integrated during the last years in international norms and regulations [1, 2]. Electric vehicles and especially cars are required today to alert their surroundings through sound, for instance when going slowly and silently on electric power. There are no formal regulations for other silent vehicles at the moment, but there is considerable discussion in society at large about the risks involved with silently approaching vehicles like electric scooters. It is not at all unlikely that the near future will require even these to emit sound.

As stated above, the long-term goal of the project will be to learn whether persons with hearing impairments exhibit different preferences than normal hearing. In the study reported here, we investigate how such specificity can be explored methodologically through an interactive museum installation where the visitor can affect the sound design

of a number of futuristic electric vehicles. We register how users tweak the sound designs we provide through an interface consisting of three circular areas on a touch-sensitive screen without written or visual explanations of the sonic manipulations taking place.

1.1 Research Environment

The study and installation took place at Tekniska (the National Museum of Science and Technology) in Stockholm with an expressed focus on playfulness and interaction for all. The installation was exhibited for more than six months in The Vision Lab in *Mega Mind*, which is a particularly accessible and interactive permanent exhibition space devoted to human senses and the brain.²

This work is the result of a collaboration between several researchers, disciplines, and institutions (art, music, design, engineering), providing a required interdisciplinary approach to the questions under study. A part of this team has been previously involved in projects that concern similar questions, e.g., in collaboration with Volvo Cars, where we developed a public audiovisual interactive installation purposed to explore its relevance as a tool for supporting the development of sound environments in future silent cars [3]. This prior experience has been most relevant to this research project.

1.2 Aim and Limitations

The aim of this paper is to demonstrate a novel approach to participatory sound design and a sound design dilemma through playful interaction involving close listening and to gain data from this process. This paper includes descriptions of the installation and interface design, including the implemented sonic textures. We also briefly describe the three sound programming environments involved and their different function.

The final target user group is people with hearing impairments. To regard this as one homogeneous group would not make sense; there are huge individual differences to account for in terms of hearing abilities, experience, preferences, use of aids, sensitivity to sound, and so on. Instead, we intend to explore how this interface can allow getting responses in the long term that demonstrate listening preferences from the individual user.

We collected visitor data during the six-month period the installation was displayed. Analyses of this data are however not included here.

2. BACKGROUND

From previous studies, we know that hearing impairments do not hinder people from enjoying everyday life activities that involve sound or are based on music, such as dancing and singing, playing audio-dependent computer games, and listening to music [4,5]. Hearing aid users even demonstrate listening abilities that outperform their typical hearing proficiency when being engaged in focused music activities [6].

The effects of environmental noise on hearing aid users are well documented: According to [7], hearing aid users found traffic machine noises to be the second most annoying sound in their environments, following human sounds which included TV and radio. Their results confirm previous studies and reiterate the established approaches towards ecological and everyday listening (e.g., [8]), as annoyance can arise from lack of observed causality when for instance you hear a machine but cannot identify the source.

Urban soundscapes have been defined as being part of the city architecture, but not only related to noise pollution [9]. The concept of soundscapes was introduced by Schafer [10] and further developed as a research area with a large impact on sound design [11]. Schulte-Fortkamp and Fiebig [12] suggested that research on environmental noise should consider how residents in the area experienced their auditive surroundings, and categorize the soundscape to identify problems and ways to address and handle these. A meta-study including seven papers [13] found that positive soundscapes did indeed have a positive effect on well-being as compared to environmental noise.

One study on musical features in soundscapes [14] found that objective parameters or descriptions of a soundscape cannot be used to predict perceptions of the sound environment, but context and localisation play significant roles in the evaluation. For instance, adding a soundscape with musical components to situations with dominant traffic noise was perceived to be annoying except in particular contexts and areas with a high presence of traffic. Jennings and Cain [15] suggest that urban soundscapes can be improved to reduce negative connotations like regarding environmental sounds as noise through addressing the needs and expectations of the users of the particular public space and to adapt a framework from the car industry, including interactive simulations.

Provocative design is a central methodological component of this project and study. It can be considered as a subset of critical design [16] and deals with possible futures. One method in provocative design is to create curiosity and engagement from ambiguity. The intended outcome of a provocative design approach is not a final product design, but a prototype or idea that provokes thought and challenges norms [17].

3. IMPLEMENTATION

In this section we describe the implementation of the installation from the relevant perspectives: technical setup at the museum, the user interface, the sound synthesis, and the soundscape design. The interface is available for testing online.³

3.1 Video and Concept

A video loop was produced to visualize the future scenario of having exotic electric vehicles moving around on streets and sidewalks, see Figure 1. There are three futuristic and hypothetical vehicles: the “hoverboard”—a flying skateboard, the “gyrochair”—a gyroscopic wheelchair

² <https://www.tekniskamuseet.se/en/discover/exhibitions/megamind/>

³ <https://hanslindetorp.github.io/WebAudioXML/demos/Ficson>

Figure 1. A screenshot of the video projected in the installation. There are three futuristic electrical vehicles that move across the whole screen in a seamless loop of 30 seconds: a “gyrochair” (left, yellow), a “hoverboard” (middle, blue), and a “hangflyer” (right, pink).

controlled by shifting body weight, and the “hangflyer”—a drone which you hang from and bounce on the ground with slow, high jumps. These are given movements and behaviours that are visually and physically convincing and suitable for looping the video seamlessly.

The video background is a semi-still image of a modern town square with human avatars walking, sitting or otherwise interacting with the surroundings. Both buildings, vegetation, avatars, and the lighting are modelled realistically to immerse the visitor in the scene (with for instance reflections, shadows, moving leaves).

3.2 Installation

The exhibition space is a room of approximately 15x6 meters with three meters up to some scaffolding with spotlights and video projectors, while the ceiling is many meters up. One wall is curved and has a 4k video projection covering the whole wall, 3840x1220 pixels. The room is dark lit with dark walls and floor painting. In the middle is a podium with a slightly tilted touchscreen of approximately 24 inches, see Figure 2.

Eight active speakers were added to the room and placed on the floor and in the overhead scaffolding, surrounding the visitors in order to create an experience as immersive as possible. Four main floor speakers are 8-inch full-range monitors, the two front overhead speakers are 4-inch full-range, and the two back overhead speakers are 5-inch full-range monitors, hidden from sight. The main speakers in front of the visitor are placed inside artistically painted boxes on the floor to augment and expand the milieu in the video and to hide the electronics.

The computer used for the installation is a Windows 10 desktop gaming PC capable of running several high resolution video outputs. Multichannel sound is sent to the speakers from an HDMI 7.1 surround extractor unit. The application is running with Node.js⁴ in a Chrome web browser, which also was an incentive for distributing the application online.

⁴ <https://nodejs.org/en/>

3.3 Interface

The touchscreen in the middle of the room is used for interacting with the sound designs. The screen shows three coloured circles with a diameter of approximately 10 cm and two smaller rectangular buttons. To guide and restrict the visitors’ actions, a laser-cut and painted cardboard plate with holes for the circles and buttons is placed on top of the touchscreen. The system restricts to reading only one finger press, see the interface in Figure 3. To avoid a bias towards letting the finger end at a point like the top of the circle, the circle is “rotated” a random number of degrees for each new participant or session.

3.4 Synthesis and Sound Design

Sound design programming, as described below, were realized in two steps. After an ideation phase using samples, ambient recordings, and several software for audio manipulation, the prototype syntheses were built and tested in Pure data [18]. This software was chosen here due to its flexibility and ability to quickly sketch and manipulate a number of sonic concepts and processes. Next, to be able to run everything within a web browser, the final version of the syntheses were reprogrammed using WebAudioXML (WAXML) [19], which is an XML language and parser for building web audio applications. All vehicle sounds are generated in real-time with native Web Audio objects like oscillators, filters, gain nodes, convolver nodes and Audio Worklets [20]. The design allows for both animation data and user interactions to manipulate any parameter of the audio configuration. The background layer was composed of three stereo files looped with different lengths that insures a background soundscape that never sounds exactly the same. We used an equal-power crossfade algorithm that allowed for dynamic positioning of the loop start and loop end during the performance.

Each vehicle sound is the result of two layers of sound juxtaposed. Layer 1 aims at representing the physical soundprint of each different engine, depicting its characteristic (fictional) mechanical/electrical textures. These sounds are

Figure 2. The layout of the room with one big screen, one touch screen interface at the center, four surround speakers (L, R, RL and RR), and four front speakers (1-4) for the vehicle sounds. The room dimensions are approximately 15x6x3 meters.

created in real-time employing filtered noise-based synthesis processes. In the case of the hoverboard this basic layer is based on the concept of air-flow, for the gyrochair it is essentially representing the electrical activity of the chair’s motor, while for the hangflyer it is focused on the rotors’ activity. This basic layer of sound responds also to a main need in terms of comprehension (and deciphering) of complex audio-visual urban representations: a strong link is provided to each vehicle, supporting the visitor’s perception in terms of recognition and localisation of moving sources.

Layer 2 is constructed to be further explored and fine-tuned by exhibition visitors. Through the interactive environment described above, each visitor will be able to choose among a series of different but related sound textures progressively ranging from nearly random-based materials—in rhythmical and harmonic terms—to highly structured ones.

The visitors are confronted to a tactile circular area per vehicle in which, by moving their finger, they are able to choose their preferred sonic texture (see Figure 3). Each axis on the circle corresponds to a different ‘family’ of sounds (four in total), and the spaces in-between provide different degrees of mixes of these sound families. Towards the outer circle, the users get the “dry” sounds presenting a high dynamic activity. As the finger move inwards, they access the “wet” version of the sounds in which, through a convolution reverb process, the dynamics are flattened out to generate more continuous textures.

From the ideation phase and based on a previous study [3] we decided to design the sounds to be inspired by engine characteristics, propulsion, and other mechanical qualities, but to also introduce non-mechanical sounds inspired by synthesis found in musical production. Finally, the implemented sound designs described here are meant to provoke

the visitor into considering other types of sounds in the future than those found in contemporary everyday life.

3.4.1 Description of the Sounds in Layer 2

Four different families of sounds were made, corresponding to a progressive degree of organisation: on one extreme more chaotic or stochastic textures, on the opposite more organised forms. In general, texture families 1 and 2 are more noise-based in perceptual terms, while the following ones are more structured and “musical” in rhythmical and harmonic terms. The user interacts with the circular area to choose among and blend these different sound materials and define the desired level of transients and dynamics: the exterior of the circle corresponding to max transients, i.e., original texture, and the interior part corresponding to a smoothed-out texture. In dynamic terms, we move from points/transients to continuous lines.

All textures will then pass through a band-pass filter that will essentially follow the actions observed on the video. As a result of this, only a part of these raw broad textures will be perceived, enhancing the feeling of acceleration/deceleration, and of relaxation/attention from the pedestrian’s perspective.

Each vehicle will have a similar but not identical set of sounds (four equivalent sonic textures) whose dynamic and spectral characteristics will then be tuned to their specific behaviour: envelope, basal tone, harmonic structure, etc. This specific design should help the observer to establish an intuitive link between each vehicle and its sounds, and distinguish them when listening to several vehicles running in parallel within the same audiovisual space.

3.4.2 Family 1

At the chaos, random or stochastic extreme, we have a texture providing a fast and random distribution of point-

Figure 3. The left image shows a close-up on the interactive touch screen with three coloured circles and two smaller rectangular buttons. The right shows a schematic overview of the two layers of sounds for each vehicle and how the mix between the sound texture families and the wet/dry balance can be controlled from the user interface.

Figure 4. A spectrogram of one of the possible sonic textures characterising each vehicle in motion (10 seconds each). From left to right: the “hoverboard”, the “gyrochair” and the “hangflyer”. These textures include both layers composing the sound of each vehicle: the mechanic/electric one as well as an added designed layer in the hands of the visitors.

frequencies. Similar to a white or pink noise in its structure, we generated here a low density version of it, where each “point” can be perceived independently. Each vehicle will be characterised by a different frequency range and envelope characteristics (attack notably for each point).

3.4.3 Family 2

The idea of the second family is to provide a texture with an “embryonic” harmonic structure, even if it is still imprecise and quite spread, whose rhythmical or dynamic form remains quite rough and undefined. The distance between the different harmonic lines is based on always having the same tonal interval for each of the examples (a major third, a fourth, a fifth). Starting from a series of “grains”, which are very short periodic pulses of a single sine tone, this sonic texture gets pitch-shifted up at a regular interval and fed back to itself, so that this interval gets repeated endlessly in the vertical dimension within the hearing range creating a harmonic structure.

The feedback process can be modified in terms of time

delay, in order to create different rhythmical textures and densities. Note, despite the term “grain”, this is not created through granular synthesis in Web Audio, only in the original Pure data prototype; however, an equivalent process was emulated.

3.4.4 Family 3

Family 3 is created through multiple band-pass filtering of the first noise-based texture (family 1) following a natural harmonic series. While presenting a clear harmonic structure, this family is characterised by a random grainy texture. As for family 1, this texture will be characterised by three different densities of points for the three different vehicles, as well as three different envelope characteristics.

3.4.5 Family 4

The fourth family has a vertical structure following the natural harmonic series. Each harmonic line is made of regular sine tone pulses presenting all the same envelope characteristics (ADSR)—but they are different and specific

to each vehicle, depicting their specific modes of motion. Each sine tone pulse is out of sync from the other frequencies, in order to avoid perceptually harmonic structures and keeping thus some vertical independence important when the band-pass filter will enter in action. Regarding rhythmic patterns, each sine tone pulse is coming back at proportionally faster tempi when going up in the spectrum.

3.4.6 Parameter Mapping

The synthesis models of the four families have a great number of parameters to control, including envelope shapes, pitch, filter cutoff frequencies, trigger rates, gain, chunk lengths, and many more. The movement information from the vehicles affect all the available parameters in a high-level control approach, and even the visitors actions utilize a high-level control of the parameters.

3.5 Environmental Sounds and Soundscape

In addition to the sound models described above, we included environmental recordings to accentuate and match the visuals. In the video there are people walking, sitting at a café table talking, and there are indications that there might be traffic behind the spectator. These sounds were between 24-27 seconds long, and looped seamlessly independent of the video looping to provide a realistic and varying soundscape.

The soundscape presented to the installation visitor contains the three vehicle sound designs and the environmental sounds. These are mixed and separated in the multichannel setup.

The final overall sound level is a few dB below the estimated actual sound level from a similar city square. It has been shown that such a reduction in sound level works best for attaining ecologically valid results from a soundscape presented in a laboratory setting [21].

3.6 Physical Implementation

The installation premiered in November 2021 in the Vision Lab at Tekniska in Stockholm and was running continuously until June 2022. Visitors were invited at an information screen to interact with the touchscreen interface placed in the middle of the room, in front of the curved video projection wall. The projected 30-second long seamlessly looped video shows the three vehicles moving across a modelled city square, making small turns and short stops. All graphics and animations have a high degree of realism to create a sense of immersion.

The multichannel sound uses eight speakers spread out in the room. Four front speakers on the floor pan sound from all the vehicles, and the hangflyer is also played from the above front speakers because of its vertical disposition. Both overhead stereo speaker pairs play the random composition of environmental sounds, but differently in the front and back channels, creating a realistic and embracing soundscape.

Visitors tweak the sound design for each vehicle using the interface on the touchscreen. Each design is accessed using the circle area where you can fade and mix between the four sound design families with different qualities, some

musical and others more engine-like. Within this circle, you even change effects such as reverberation and filtering. In addition to the sound design, vehicle sounds are affected by how they move, depending on their characteristics, i.e., their horizontal and vertical movement speeds, acceleration, turns, heading, and stopping. These characteristics are connected to the propulsion and imagined engine, as well as their appearance and role; for instance, the gyrochair and its handling resembles existing vehicles while the hangflyer does not.

The interaction has been programmed and implemented to make it as easy as possible in order to invite all museum visitors to participate. On the touchscreen, you can only move around within three differently coloured circles that represent the three correspondingly coloured vehicles on the main screen, and also, for data collection purposes, click two buttons marked with “I’m done” and “Restart”.

4. RESULTS

The combination of a realistic video, full-wall projection, multichannel surrounding sound, physical objects to hide electronics, a minimalist interaction device, and complex sounds to change, provided the visitor with a rich immersive experience. The setup furthermore provided an operational environment for the visitors to interact efficiently with the given sonic materials and sonic environment i.e., to intuitively understand the effect of their actions in terms of perceived sonic manipulations, as well as to provide feedback on the material by selecting their preferred textures for each vehicle. According to our observations, all these operations took place within a very limited amount of time (under 1 minute per vehicle) and without the need for any specific introduction or explanation. As introduced before, two strategies were chosen to that aim that can be considered now as relevant choices: limiting the number of graphic elements that the visitor could interact with (only one controller per vehicle), as well as working carefully on the spatial mapping (distinct localisation) of each vehicle and sound source.

The implementation of this project on a web-based programming environment also provided broad flexibility and portability, allowing both a complex public installation or a more individual experience in pedagogic as well as domestic environments. Its current permanent online format⁵ effectively allows continued data gathering, which can be analyzed and used to improve the tested environment and materials. With the project we have demonstrated the potential of Web Audio as a platform for programming powerful real-time audio engines that can match more conventional solutions like Pure data, Max/MSP and Supercollider. As mentioned before, the main advantages are the portability and scalability we get, offered natively by running in a web browser. Also, for a museum or other external collaborator, having a browser-based exhibition instead of being dependent on installing specific software that may need updating is welcome.

The sound synthesis and audio system setup have many

⁵ <https://hanslindetorp.github.io/WebAudioXML/demos/Ficson>

novel implementations. One of the technically challenging issues was to get multichannel sound out using Chrome and Windows OS. Our final solution to use an HDMI extractor was largely untested in Web Audio. In terms of system performance, we got good results and stable audio-visual rendering without glitches from using the Chrome browser. Another considerable development was a descriptive language to connect time to animation data, and animation data to audio parameters.

5. DISCUSSION

As a result of the approach with four synthesis families per vehicle, the visitors have much freedom in playing the sound design or navigating with the design space we have defined. Many of the resulting sounds are much more musical in nature than what you could expect from a vehicle's engine. However, we have not conformed to standard musical ideals or traditional structures in melodic or rhythmic terms, which could have produced a displaced or at least excessively staged experience. Our aim was to still focus on the potentially existing vehicle sounds and, by means of this added layer, transform their character, perception, potential meaning and as a result, function. The combination of the different families of sounds should allow the visitor to create specific designed textures able to challenge how a vehicle sound should be and how does it operate within a complex urban environment.

For hearing impaired, there is a provocative side to the designs as they are mostly quite salient. The experience also rather compels you to add more sound to the soundscape than you would do if presented with a number of sliders that could control the sound level only, as we know that turning down the noise is a go-to solution. And the sounds can indeed take very different forms that are not necessarily engine-like. Through this operation, we argue that we face the visitor with a dilemma of exposing or attenuating sounds. The dilemma is connected to the conflict between appreciating and making sense of the activity in the (virtual) environment.

It is not unlikely that data collected from such an installation will be ambiguous or in other ways hard to draw conclusions from. With the above described implementation, it is however uncomplicated to update the installation at any time with new sound material or mappings to test. We expect to need several iterations in order to understand sound appreciation and preferences of persons with hearing impairments in our context.

One of the possible outcomes is that sound designs created by hearing impaired do not differ from those created by persons with normal hearing. The implication would be that it does not matter much who will make sound designs for future electrical vehicles. Another possible outcome is that the design will differ—the next step is then to see if persons with hearing impairments also prefer designs created by hearing impaired, or if they prefer designs created by normal hearing. This will have direct implications for the sound design profession.

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